

THYROID DISEASES: HYPOTHYROIDISM AND HYPERTHYROIDISM

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Abstract: This article provides information on thyroid disorders, including hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism.

Key words: dysgenesis, hypoplasia, endemic bukok, colds, thyroidectomy,

Classification of diseases of the CALCONIMON GLAND (KB).

I. Thyrotoxicosis syndrome:

1. Glandular hypersecretion of hormones (diffuse toxic cyst, thyrotoxic adenoma, cystic nodule and disseminated functional autonomy, iodine-induced, TTG-induced thyrotoxicosis and gestational transient thyrotoxicosis);
2. With increased synthesis of thyroid hormones outside the gland (Struma ovarii, metastases of gland cancer);
3. It is not associated with excessive production of glandular hormones (iatrogenic and artificial thyrotoxicosis, de Kerven's subacute thyroiditis in the stage of thyrotoxicosis).

II. Hypothyroidism syndrome:

1. Primary - hypothyroidism with a decrease in the amount of functional gland tissue (nodular hypothyroidism, postoperative, atrophic form of autoimmune thyroiditis, postradiation, acute subacute viral injury, due to tumors and others);
2. Central (pituitary genesis and hypothalamic genesis) hypothyroidism;

III. Thyroid goiter with intact activity: euthyroid goiter, thyroid neoplasia - dangerous and safe, thyroiditis.

TOXIC BUKOC is a genetic disease caused by the production of thyroid hormones in large quantities.

Etiology - unknown;

Predisposing factors - infectious and mental injuries, insolation, stressful situations.

Pathogenesis - a defect of the immune system (mutation of the enhanced T-lymphocyte clone, their cytotoxic effect on KB;

Production of antibodies by V-lymphocytes and their stimulation of KB - thyrostimulating ATs).

1. Light heart rate (pulse - less than 100 beats per minute, basic

metabolism did not exceed 30%, signs of disease not manifest);

2. Average heart rate (pulse beats -100-120 times per minute, basic metabolism is 30-60%, body weight is slightly reduced);

3. Heavy heart attack (pulse over -120, sometimes oscillating).

symptoms such as arrhythmia, heart failure, and liver damage decrease, and metabolism of the main substance exceeds 60%, body weight decreases sufficiently).

Thyrotoxic crisis represents the greatest danger for Khaet.

HYPOTHYROIDISM is a disease caused by insufficient or no production of thyroid hormones in the thyroid gland.

According to the reasons for the emergence:

- primary (the pathological process is located in the heart).

Reasons: abnormalities in gland development, dysgenesis, hypoplasia, endemic bukok, colds, thyroidectomy, taking thyroid drugs;

According to the reasons for the emergence:

- secondary (the pathological process is observed in the pituitary gland).

Causes: tumors, infection, injury;

- tertiary (the pathological process is observed in the hypothalamus).

Causes: tumors, infection, injury.

Antibodies against thyroid hormones (TZ and T4) are produced in the peripheral tissue, or as a result of the reduction of nuclear receptors, intolerance to the effects of thyroid hormones occurs in peripheral tissues.

- Classification of primary hypothyroidism according to severity
- Latent (subclinical): TTG amount is high, T-4 amount is normal;
- Manifest: hypersecretion of TTG, low amount of T-4:

clinical manifestations:

- compensated; - decompensated.

3. Weight loss (complicated): cretinism, heart failure.

Characteristics of secondary hypothyroidism compared to primary hypothyroidism:

- Metabolic-hypothermic syndrome without obesity, sometimes it can be accompanied by weight loss;
- Dermopathy of poorly developed, solitary tumors weight, thin skin, weight loss;
- Insufficiency of blood circulation, hypothyroid polyserositis, hepatomegaly, V-12 deficiency anemia does not occur.

Severe complications of hypothyroidism

(hypothyroid or myxedematous coma)

- Contingent encounter: patients who have not been treated at all or have been treated incorrectly, are often observed in 60-80-year-old women in the cold season of the year, in various stressful situations.

Cause: total or sudden lack of thyroid hormones.

- Predisposing factors: various colds, concomitant diseases (cardiovascular system deficiency, various fevers), drug sedation, severe cold.

- Mechanism of action: lack of thyroid hormones, reduction of brain metabolism, development of hypoxia, reduction of oxygen, carbohydrate, fat, salt and water metabolism, functional change of internal organs.

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